

Data extraction instrument: The nexus of health and labour exploitation among migrant populations in the Eastern Mediterranean region and Türkiye: a scoping review

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Document/study characteristics

1. Title of paper
2. Year of publication
3. Author
4. Affiliation
5. Origin/country of origin (where the source was published or conducted)
6. Document type
 - a) Empirical study
 - b) Report
 - c) Thesis or dissertations
 - d) Review
 - e) Policy paper
 - f) Editorial
 - g) Commentary
 - h) Protocol
 - i) Other, specify
7. Study population source
8. Sample size
 - a) <50
 - b) 50-100
 - c) 101-200
 - d) >200
9. Study aim
10. Methodology/methods – text
11. Date data were collected

Context

12. Country

- Afghanistan
- Bahrain
- Djibouti
- Egypt
- Iran
- Iraq
- Jordan
- Kuwait
- Lebanon
- Libya
- Morocco
- Oman
- Pakistan
- Qatar
- Saudi Arabia
- Somalia
- Sudan
- Syria
- Tunisia
- United Arab Emirates
- Yemen
- Türkiye
- Others: (in case of reviews)

13. Setting where the study was conducted - text

Population characteristics

14. Age group

- a) <18
- b) 18 – 25
- c) 26 – 35
- d) 36 – 45
- e) 46 – 55
- f) 56 – 65
- g) > 65 (above retirement age)

15. Gender identity

- a) Woman
- b) Man
- c) Transgender
- d) Non-binary/non-conforming
- e) Not listed, text

16. Sexuality

- a) Asexual
- b) Bisexual
- c) Gay
- d) Heterosexual
- e) Lesbian
- f) Pansexual
- g) Queer
- h) Not listed, text

17. Race or ethnicity

- a) Arab
- b) Kurd
- c) Persian
- d) Black
- e) White
- f) South Asian
- g) East Asian
- h) North African
- i) Sub-Saharan African
- j) Eastern European
- k) Afghan
- l) Turk

18. Country of origin

- a) Syria
- b) Afghanistan
- c) Iraq
- d) Pakistan
- e) India
- f) Iran
- g) Egypt
- h) Jordan
- i) Palestine
- j) Tunisia
- k) Morocco
- l) Sudan
- m) South Sudan
- n) Eritrea
- o) Nigeria

- p) Guinea
- q) Côte d'Ivoire
- r) Mali
- s) Burkina Faso
- t) Cameroon
- u) Yemen
- v) Lebanon
- w) Philippines
- x) Other, please indicate

19. Host country

- a) Afghanistan
- b) Bahrain
- c) Djibouti
- d) Egypt
- e) Iran (Islamic Republic of)
- f) Iraq
- g) Jordan
- h) Kuwait
- i) Lebanon
- j) Libya
- k) Morocco
- l) Oman
- m) Pakistan
- n) Palestine
- o) Qatar
- p) Saudi Arabia
- q) Somalia
- r) Sudan
- s) Syrian Arab Republic

- t) Tunisia
- u) Türkiye
- v) United Arab Emirates
- w) Yemen

20. Migratory status

- a) Undocumented
- b) Stateless
- c) Refugee or Asylum Seeker (granted)
- d) Asylum Seeker (pending)
- e) Temporary Visa Holder (e.g., work, student)
- f) Economic migrant
- g) Other, specify

21. Employment status

- a) Formally employed
- b) Unemployed
- c) Self-employed
- d) Informally employed
- e) Part-time job
- f) Fulltime job
- g) Combines more than one job in parallel

22. Language - text

23. Sociocultural factors - text

Concept

24. Labour exploitation

- a) Labour exploitation perpetrator: (text)
- b) Typology of labour exploitation
 - 1. Forced labour

2. Debt bondage
 3. Human trafficking
 4. Wage theft
 5. Excessive working hours
 6. Unsafe working conditions
 7. Other, specify
- c) Typology of violence
1. Structural violence
 2. Symbolic violence
 3. Interpersonal violence
- d) How is this typology of violence manifested? (text)
- e) Industry or sector involved
1. Agriculture and farming
 2. Construction
 3. Accommodation and food service
 4. Fishing
 5. Forestry (logging)
 6. Textile and clothing manufacturing sector
 7. Domestic work
 8. Retail and service
 9. Sex work and social escort
 10. Mining
 11. Other
- f) Recruitment methods: (text)
25. Duration of exploitation
- a) <6 months
 - b) 6-12 months
 - c) 1-3 years
 - d) >3 years

- e) Not specified
26. Position on the labour exploitation continuum:
- a) Decent work conditions (good standards, fair wages, freedom of expression, social protections)
 - b) Less than decent working conditions (within legal limits, but hard conditions and low wages)
 - c) Exploitative conditions (breaching labour laws, but workers can leave)
 - d) Severe exploitation (criminal/human rights law violations, workers cannot leave without reprisals)
 - e) Forced labour/human trafficking (coercion, confinement, physical violence, severe exploitation)
27. Describe any movement along the continuum or factors contributing to the position on the continuum. Text
28. Other than the migratory status, did any of the following additional factors contribute to experiences of labour exploitation? How? (text)
- a) Age
 - b) Gender
 - c) Sexuality
 - d) Race and/or Ethnicity
 - e) Religion
 - f) Level of education
 - g) Socioeconomic condition
 - h) Disability
 - i) Other, specify
29. Health outcomes
- a) Physical health outcomes in relation to labour exploitation
 - 1. Musculoskeletal disorders – indicate examples
 - 2. Respiratory issues – indicate examples
 - 3. Infectious diseases – indicate examples
 - 4. Physical disability – indicate examples
 - 5. Malnutrition
 - 6. Other (specify)
 - b) Mental health outcomes in relation to labour exploitation
 - 1. Depression
 - 2. Anxiety

3. PTSD
4. Substance abuse
5. Other (specify)

c) Impacts on psychosocial and physical wellbeing in relation to labour exploitation – text

30. Access to healthcare in relation to labour exploitation

1. Timely
2. Delayed
3. No access

b) Effective coverage¹:

Tanahashi coverage domain	Types of barriers that can be experienced across the continuum of health services, with the respective shorthand code for data processing	Tick the box and mention the encountered barriers in relation to the framework dimensions
Availability	Insufficient number or density of health facilities [code: facility]	
	No outreach mechanisms/ community-based service points [code: outreach]	
	Insufficient supply and appropriate stock of health workers with the competencies (including through access to ongoing training) and skill-mix to match the health needs of the population [code: HW mix and competencies];	
	Lack of equitable distribution of health workers taking into account the demographic composition, rural-urban mix and underserved areas or populations [code: HW distribution]	
	Inadequate supply of medicines to meet population needs [code: medications availability]	

¹ This table is copied from the evidence synthesis framework of the WHO's handbook for conducting assessments of barriers to effective coverage with health services: in support of equity-oriented reforms towards universal health coverage (WHO, 2014).

	Scarcity or poor quality of, or insufficient maintenance of, necessary equipment (e.g. equipment for examinations, wheelchairs for patients, etc.) or equipment not appropriate for differing biological (age, sex) needs and local reality [code: equipment]	
	Weak laboratory system or inadequate cold chain [code: lab cold chain]	
	Services not available in any location perceived as close enough to be realistically reachable for the given health condition of concern (e.g. cancer services only available in capital city or abroad, gender-based violence and mental health services only available in capital) [code: no service]	
	Inadequate ambulance services and/or transport methods/vehicles for mobile health units/home care visits [code: no med vehicle]	
	Shortage or poorly functioning basic amenities such as electrification, improved water and sanitation, and waste management in health facilities [code: amenities]	
	Lack of adequate computer equipment, internet connectivity and phone services (including for outreach services, telemedicine) for either provider or patient [code: ITC equipment]	
	Other examples in the study that were not mentioned above, please describe (text)	
	<i>This includes the unavailability of same-gender and/or culturally competent and linguistically appropriate providers where needed – which is classified as both an availability- and acceptability-related barrier.</i>	
Accessibility	Geographic and physical	
	<i>Long distance and time for travelling to health service point [code: travel time]</i>	
	<i>Lack of appropriate mode of transport [code: travel method]</i>	
	<i>Unsafe terrain or weather conditions, impassable roads due to quality, road blockages due to conflict/insecurity, unsafe location of service point [code: unsafe conditions]</i>	
	<i>Limited accessibility of facilities for persons with disabilities [code: disabilities]</i>	
	Other examples in the study that were not mentioned above, please describe (text)	
	Financial	
<i>Direct: official out-of-pocket expenditures for services (e.g. co-payment for services, laboratory tests, exams) [code: direct service costs]</i>		

	<i>Direct: official out-of-pocket expenditures for medicines and health products (e.g. assistive devices) [code: direct medprod costs]</i>	
	<i>Indirect: transport and accommodation costs linked to using services [code: indirect transport costs]</i>	
	<i>Indirect: opportunity costs (e.g. lost work, cost of child/older person care during absence, paying someone to do one's job during absence, such as managing livestock/farm) [code: indirect opportunity costs]</i>	
	<i>Informal payments (cash or in-kind) [code: informal payments]</i>	
	<i>Public health service capacity and provider incentive structure influencing patients' use of private services [code: private public interface]</i>	
	<i>Other examples in the study that were not mentioned above, please describe (text)</i>	
	<i>Organizational and informational</i>	
	<i>Opening times are not in synergy with when people are available to access services [code: opening times]</i>	
	<i>Inadequate systems to schedule appointments and long waiting times/lack of timeliness [code: scheduling]</i>	
	<i>Exclusionary administrative requirements for care (e.g. registration in local area) [code: registration]</i>	
	<i>Lack of access to culturally and linguistically appropriate health information that considers local populations' world views and cultural practices [code: culturally relevant info]</i>	
	<i>Delivery of health information not considering the most appropriate communication modalities in light of illiteracy rates, limited access to technology and internet connectivity, preferred use of TV or radio over written materials, etc. [code: communication modality]</i>	
	<i>Lack of awareness by potential service users of rights and obligations [code: rights awareness]</i>	

	<i>Challenges of working in the informal economy (e.g. no paid sick leave to go to an appointment) [code: informal economy]</i>	
	<i>See Acceptability for: barriers related to power dynamics and inequalities (e.g. resulting in lack of autonomy to make decisions about one's own health) and fear of/previous experiences of discrimination based on gender, ethnicity, Indigeneity and other grounds that make people not want to access services</i>	
Acceptability	<i>Lack of alignment with cultural beliefs and preferences (e.g. preference for traditional medicine, differing views of health and illness) and coordination/integration with Indigenous/traditional medicine systems [code: culturally acceptable services]</i>	
	<i>Gender norms, roles, power and relations that inhibit access (e.g. limited autonomy of some women in deciding when to seek care, the patient only being allowed to or wanting to see a same-gender provider, or gender norms on masculinity that delay treatment-seeking) [code: gender norms]</i>	
	<i>Limited provision of age-appropriate services (e.g. adolescent-friendly services not being provided) [code: age-relevant]</i>	
	<i>Lack of services and health products that account for biological differences by sex (e.g. cardiovascular disease services that do not account for specific differences in the manifestation of symptoms of a heart attack between sexes) [code: biological differences]</i>	
	<i>Negative perceptions of service quality (including the quality dimensions of equity, safety, effectiveness, people-centredness, efficiency, timeliness and integration) [code: quality perceptions]</i>	
	<i>Low levels of trust in the health system (linked to perceptions of transparency and accountability, fear of criminalisation or other social and legal repercussions, and experience with corruption) [code: trust]</i>	
	<i>Discriminatory attitudes by providers (e.g. based on sex, gender, ethnicity, marital status, religion, caste, disability, health status or sexual orientation of the person seeking care) [code: discrimination]</i>	
	<i>Perceived/actual extent to which confidentiality is protected [code: confidentiality]</i>	

	<i>Low attractiveness of health services compared to alternative/competing options for using one's time and resources (e.g. health promotion services are available and accessible but less attractive compared to other activities) [code: prioritisation]</i>	
Contact coverage	Contact coverage refers to the actual contact between the service provider and the user when services are available, accessible and acceptable	
Effective coverage	<i>Lack of diagnostic accuracy (influenced by lack of diagnostic equipment and other factors such as gender unequal/blind protocols) [code: diagnostic capacity]</i>	
	<i>Insufficient provider compliance (e.g. related to low levels of training, lack of supportive system requirements such as protocols and guidelines, and deficient overall quality control mechanisms) [code: provider compliance]</i>	
	<i>Lack of timeliness (e.g. in an emergency, triage, assessment and intervention processes must be of sufficient speed such that time-sensitive health conditions are recognized and treated as soon as possible) [code: timeliness]</i>	
	<i>Weak referral and back-referral systems [code: referrals]</i>	
	<i>Inadequate treatment adherence (e.g. due to unclear instructions, poor patient-provider relationship, mismatch between treatment prescribed and patient compliance ability, adverse social conditions and gender roles/relations) [code: patient adherence]</i>	
	<i>Stigmatization caused by service usage that disrupts treatment adherence and/or otherwise negatively impacts patients' health [code: stigmatization]</i>	
	<i>Limited effectiveness of the interventions due to inappropriate service delivery for the differing biological, circumstantial (e.g. physical environment) and cultural reality of the patient [code: appropriateness]</i>	
	<i>Healthcare-associated infection occurring in a patient during the process of care in a hospital or other healthcare facility which was not present or incubating at the time of admission [code: infection]</i>	
	<i>Link to financial protection dimension of UHC: catastrophic/ impoverishing expenditures or detrimental sale of assets incurred during the process of care that force the patient to stop treatment before it is completed</i>	

31. Coping strategies – text
 - a) Existing support network - text
32. Brief description of aspects/dimensions of health and/or access to healthcare impacts assessed and found in relation to labour exploitation
33. Brief description of promising healthcare practices or interventions mentioned addressing labour exploitation in migrant populations
34. Key findings that relate to the scoping review question.
35. Rationale of exclusion
 - a) The study focuses only on sex trafficking.
 - b) The study focuses on labour exploitation in populations other than migrants.
 - c) The study focuses on labour exploitation in migrant populations without addressing associated health issues.
 - d) The study focuses on migrants' health without addressing labour exploitation.
 - e) The study focuses on populations outside of the geographic scope.